

Information and Quantum $\exp(ipx)$ - The Importance of X Information Part II

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The spatial probability for the position of a stationary object in a length L is $P(x)dx=dx/L$. This probability is sometimes linked to constant momentum or speed. In such a case, $\ln(P(x)) = \ln(L)$ and so L is really the only information in this scenario, not p (momentum) or x . We argued in Part I, however, that both p and x should physically represent information and moreover that one should take px to be information so that in the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem, one may take a $V1-V2$ constant potential junction to be at $x=0$ so that $p_{incident} x = p_{reflected} x = p_{refracted} x = 0$, even though the p values are all different. We argue that given that E is the same for all, there should be an intrinsic information linked to p which is also the same, and argued for px .

In this note, we examine $\ln(P(x))=\ln(L)$ which does consider p or x . Given that px should be information, it seems that to be consistent with $\ln(P(x))$ one has to consider no motion, i.e. px and $-px$ together in an AND situation with probabilities. This suggests $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ as a second probability.

We note that if $y=px$, then the probability is $\exp(iy)/\sqrt{L}$. Given that this combines with $\exp(-iy)/\sqrt{L}$ in a product, we argue that it is really L and the sign of y that are key pieces of information in $\exp(iy)/\sqrt{L}$. Furthermore, one may see that $d/dy \exp(iy) = i \exp(iy)$, which essentially brings out the sign of y .

If p is constant, then d/dy is equivalent to $1/p d/dx$ and one does not need to know p or x , but only the sign of $y=px$. (Note: $d/dy = 1/p d/dx$.) One might expect $P1(y)$ (where $P1(y)=\exp(iy)/\sqrt{L}$) to contain both p and $-p$ with equal probabilities, but arranged in such a manner that the proper overall sign appears. In other words, we argue that $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px) = .5 (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) + i .5 (\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx))$. Given that the overall sign of p in $\exp(ipx)$ is key if x is positive, one expects both p and $-p$ in the expression of $P1(px)$ because p is not the critical piece of information if one uses $y=px$. Thus, in order to create an eigenfunction of d/dy one needs both two dimensions and p and $-p$ pieces.

We argued in a previous note that the presence of $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ is equivalent to two momenta which differ, i.e. a lack of conservation of momentum. We suggest that this feature exists even for a constant p , i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ separately, but is not completely apparent because one has two dimensions. It is, however, key for two-slit interference.

$P(x)dx = dx/L$

If one has an interval of length L , then a uniform distribution of stationary objects is given by:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad ((1))$$

$P(x)$ does not depend on either p or x , but L is really the only information present. Formally,

$$\text{Information} = \ln(P(x)) = \ln(L) \quad ((2)).$$

It seems, however, that p and x are both pieces of information, whether or not they appear in $P(x)$. In Part I, we argued that one must in fact take the product:

$$\text{Information} = y = px \quad ((3))$$

in order to handle the problem of one-dimensional reflection-refraction. This was due to the fact that E (energy) for an incident, reflected and refracted particle are the same, suggesting the same information, but p values are not, suggesting different intrinsic information. In order to allow p 's to represent the same information one may use $y=px$ and $x=0$ as the junction point between V_1 and V_2 (constant potentials).

If one wishes to make ((3)) consistent with ((2)), one needs to stress that ((2)) is based on a stationary object and so use information from both p and $-p$ together, i.e. an AND product probability. Using ((3)), we have $\exp(iy)$ as a probability with a constant magnitude. One may note that:

$$d/dy \ln(\exp(iy)) = i \quad ((4))$$

The two dimensionality, i.e. "i", follows from a probability that does not grow indefinitely with y in order to be compatible with ((2)).

Thus, d/dxy seems to bring out the sign of y . Given that $P(x)$ is not interested in either the value of p or x , we suggest that L and the sign of p become important pieces of information.

If p is a constant, then $d/dy = 1/p d/dx$ ((5)).

If only the sign of y is important, then it seems that $P_1(y)$ ($P_1 = \exp(iy)$) should manifest this sign, but not be particularly associated with p . In other words, $P_1(px)$ could be associated with both p and $-p$, even though it chooses the sign of one or the other (as this is relevant information).

If y is information, then $y = \ln(\exp(iy))$ so $\exp(iy)$. This is two dimensional because one has:

$$d/dy \exp(iy) = \exp(iy) \quad ((6))$$

d/dy is the slope of a function. If one represents a real function as a power series of y , then d/dy lowers each y and brings in a coefficient. This leads to $\exp(y)$ as a real solution, but this grows indefinitely in y and cannot be compatible with ((2)). Thus, the complex two-dimensional value $\exp(iy)$ is needed.

Here we suggest that one does not only have two dimensions, but pieces of p and $-p$ even if one sign is chosen, i.e.

$\exp(ipx)$ means the positive sign is chosen, but:

$$\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px) = .5 (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) + .5i (\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)) \quad ((7))$$

$\exp(ipx)$, perhaps surprisingly, contains both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, but displays the correct sign, +.

The real term suggests that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are on the same footing, i.e. that one has either a particle moving to the right or left. The imaginary term is like an incident and reflected particle with the same weights, but the reflected piece as a 3.14 phase shift. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is positive in the imaginary term, it is this value which shows that motion is to the right. The -1 amplitude of $\exp(-ipx)$ suggests reflection. Thus, it is the imaginary term which shows the direction of motion and involves an incident and reflected particle term. The real term contains both as if one does not know if the particle moves to the right or left. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$, seems to be more complicated than it first appears.

Conservation of Momentum

One may note that $\exp(-iy)\exp(iy)=1$ which is linked to $P(x) = 1/L$. If, however, one writes:

$\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ipx)$ then one has: $\cos((-p_1+p)x) + i \sin((-p_1+p)x)$ ((7))

In other words, a lack of conservation of momentum, i.e. differing p values namely p_1 and p , lead to the \cos and \sin terms. Thus, given that $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$, even though there is one p value here, we argue that to be consistent one should think in terms of two p values, namely p and $-p$ as in ((7)) and this leads to the idea of non-conservation of momentum, i.e. two p values ($-p$, and p) which are not being distinguished in \cos or \sin by themselves, but allow for p and its sign to appear in a two dimensional combination.

We note that the $\cos + i \sin$ form in ((7)) may arise from a product of $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ipx)$. For a sum $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = \cos(px)$ which shows that the two p 's differ, i.e. p and $-p$.

Alternatively, a two-slit interference pattern appears because one has two different momentum vectors (and r vectors), one from each slit to the same point on a screen. The interference pattern is a signature of this difference in momenta and we argue that $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ should treat $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ separately in the same manner, i.e. as a case of two different momenta, even though at first glance one only has p .

In words, it seems that the description of p in one direction may actually involve p and $-p$ in a certain manner ((7)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that $P(x)dx = dx/L$ does not use p or x as information, only $\ln(L)$. We have argued in Part I, however, that p and x are information and that in fact they should be combined as $y=px$ so that one may analyse the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem in terms of different p values representing the same information px for $x=0$. Thus, y is information and this corresponds to $P_1(y)=\exp(iy)$ if one does not want the probability to grow indefinitely with y which would be incompatible with $P(x)=1/L$. We suggest that $P(x)$ applies to a stationary particle and so one needs $\exp(iy)\exp(-iy)$ to describe $P(x)$. In other words, it is the sign of y which becomes a very important piece of information. If this is the case, then one may suggest

that $P_1(y)$ should demonstrate the sign of y without picking a distinct p , i.e. p and $-p$ may both be part of the function such that the overall sign $+$ appears. This must be combined with a two dimensional P_1 .

Thus: $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px) = .5 (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) + .5i (\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx))$.
The real term treats p and $-p$ on the same footing whereas the second term shows that one has an incident $\exp(ipx)$ and a reflected $\exp(-ipx)$, hence the -1 coefficient. Thus, both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ appear in an expression for $\exp(ipx)$ such that the proper sign appears which is governed by the complex term.

We suggest this kind of interpretation because it is linked with a lack of momentum conservation. For example, $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ suggests momentum conservation, while $\exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ does not and leads to $\cos((-p_1+p_2)x) + i \sin((-p_1+p_2)x)$. Furthermore, two slit interference displays an interference pattern because of different p and r vectors leading to different information pieces.. Thus, we suggest that the $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ pieces of $\exp(ipx)$ be interpreted in a similar manner.